

Supplementary Material

Medical artificial intelligence research is misaligned with global disease burden: a bibliometric analysis of 197,844 publications

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S1 Table. Sensitivity analyses

Analysis	Spearman r_s	p -value	n diseases	Notes
Main analysis (Global DALYs 2021)	0.477	<0.001	115	Primary analysis
Excluding COVID-19	0.463	2.11×10^{-7}	114	Mismatch not a pandemic artefact
Pre-pandemic (2015–2019)	0.357	1.42×10^{-4}	109	Lower alignment pre-COVID
DALYs from 2022	0.480	5.72×10^{-8}	115	Stable across DALY years
DALYs from 2023	0.475	8.01×10^{-8}	115	Stable across DALY years
Deaths instead of DALYs	0.603	3.14×10^{-10}	90	Better alignment with mortality
Strict mapping (single-disease only)	0.466	1.58×10^{-7}	115	Robust to multi-disease handling
Loose mapping (whole-count)	0.481	5.12×10^{-8}	115	Robust to counting method
Low SDI DALYs	0.239	1.01×10^{-2}	115	AI poorly aligned with LIC burden
High SDI DALYs	0.619	1.73×10^{-13}	115	AI well aligned with HIC burden
Kendall τ	0.331	1.54×10^{-7}	115	Robust to correlation metric

Analysis	Spearman r_s	p -value	n diseases	Notes
Pearson r (log-transformed)	0.513	4.46×10^{-9}	115	Robust to correlation metric
Sub-period 2015–2017	0.342	5.97×10^{-4}	97	Stable across sub-periods
Sub-period 2018–2020	0.435	2.03×10^{-6}	110	Stable across sub-periods
Sub-period 2021–2023	0.446	7.24×10^{-7}	113	Stable across sub-periods
Sub-period 2024–2025	0.479	6.77×10^{-8}	114	Stable across sub-periods

S2 Table. Research Attention Index for all 115 diseases

Rank	Disease	Publications	DALYs (millions)	RAI	$\log_2(\text{RAI})$	GBD Level 1
1	Malignant skin melanoma	2,757	1.7	53.18	5.73	NCD
2	Leprosy	18	0.02	27.31	4.77	Communicable
3	Thyroid cancer	742	1.5	16.98	4.09	NCD
4	Inflammatory bowel disease	746	1.5	16.14	4.01	NCD
5	Multiple sclerosis	465	1.0	15.01	3.91	NCD
6	Brain and CNS cancer	3,604	9.2	13.06	3.71	NCD
7	Breast cancer	7,091	22.5	10.50	3.39	NCD
8	Parkinson's disease	1,817	7.4	8.19	3.03	NCD
9	Atrial fibrillation and flutter	1,931	8.7	7.38	2.88	NCD
10	Prostate cancer	1,557	8.4	6.15	2.62	NCD
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108	Anxiety disorders	46	45.6	0.034	-4.90	NCD
109	Dietary iron deficiency	38	39.9	0.032	-4.97	Communicable

Rank	Disease	Publications	DALYs (millions)	RAI	$\log_2(\text{RAI})$	GBD Level 1
110	Diarrheal diseases	56	61.8	0.031	-5.03	Communicable
111	Rheumatic heart disease	14	14.8	0.030	-5.04	NCD
112	Drowning	16	18.2	0.029	-5.09	Injuries
113	Typhoid and paratyphoid	6	7.0	0.028	-5.13	Communicable
114	Road injuries	57	74.7	0.025	-5.30	Injuries
115	Conduct disorder	2	4.7	0.014	-6.14	NCD

Full table with all 115 diseases is provided in the online data repository.

S3 Table. Year-by-year summary statistics

Year	Total papers	Mapped papers	Mapped %	Diseases identified	Spearman	
					r_s	Gini coefficient
2015	1,541	465	30.2%	71	0.301	0.673
2016	2,109	707	33.5%	83	0.280	0.854
2017	3,299	1,229	37.3%	82	0.203	0.716
2018	6,276	2,224	35.4%	95	0.369	0.757
2019	10,694	3,920	36.7%	99	0.347	0.740
2020	15,805	6,725	42.5%	102	0.352	0.733
2021	21,727	9,791	45.1%	106	0.396	0.723
2022	25,912	11,641	44.9%	109	0.442	0.728
2023	31,156	13,246	42.5%	111	0.415	0.739
2024	36,452	15,678	43.0%	109	0.397	0.736
2025	42,873	18,985	44.3%	113	0.470	0.727

S6 Table. Dataset readiness comparison: over-studied vs counter-example diseases

Disease	Dataset	Readiness score (/8)	Samples	RAI	Group
Skin melanoma	ISIC Archive / HAM10000	8	100,000	53.2	Over-studied
Breast cancer	CBIS-DDSM / INbreast / BreakHis	7	11,000	10.5	Over-studied

Disease	Dataset	Readiness score (/8)	Samples	RAI	Group
Blindness and vision loss	EyePACS / MESSIDOR / DRIVE	7	88,000	6.1	Over-studied
Lung cancer	LIDC-IDRI / LUNA16	6	1,018	3.0	Over-studied
Brain and CNS cancer	BraTS	5	2,000	13.1	Over-studied
Parkinson's disease	PPMI	4	1,500	8.2	Over-studied
Ischaemic heart disease	PTB-XL / MIT-BIH	6	21,799	0.9	Counter-example
Malaria	NIH Malaria Cell Images	5	27,558	0.3	Counter-example
Tuberculosis	Shenzhen/Montgomery CXR	4	800	0.6	Counter-example
Stroke	ATLAS	3	655	0.5	Counter-example
Oral disorders	UFBA-UESC dental radiographs	3	1,500	0.6	Counter-example
Depressive disorders	AVEC / DAIC-WOZ	1	189	0.5	Counter-example

Readiness score: sample size (0–3), standardised protocol (0–1), ML competition (0–1), imaging modality (0–1), open access (0–1), classification task (0–1). Over-studied median: 6/8; counter-example median: 4/8 (Mann–Whitney $p = 0.018$).

Supplementary Figures

Figure 1: S1 Fig. AI research alignment by income group.

S1 Fig. AI research alignment with disease burden by income group. AI publications plotted against Low SDI disease burden (A; $r_s = 0.239$) and High SDI disease burden (B; $r_s = 0.619$).

Figure 2: S2 Fig. AI method distribution by disease.

S2 Fig. AI method distribution by disease (heatmap). Percentage of each disease’s papers using each AI method type across the top 20 diseases by publication count.

Figure 3: S3 Fig. Predictors of AI research attention.

S3 Fig. Predictors of AI research attention (forest plot). Standardised regression coefficients from multivariable OLS model predicting \log_{10} (AI publications) across 38 diseases.

Figure 4: S4 Fig. Temporal trend in alignment.

S4 Fig. Temporal trend in AI research–burden alignment (2015–2025). Annual Spearman r_s between publication share and DALY share with linear trend line.

S1 Text. Corrective mechanism modelling details

The corrective model assumes that total medical research is a mixture of general medical research and AI research:

$$\text{Combined distribution} = (1 - \alpha) \times \text{General distribution} + \alpha \times \text{AI distribution}$$

where α is AI's share of total medical research. The targeted-dataset scenario modified the AI distribution by setting the publication share for the 10 most under-studied diseases to $\text{target RAI} \times \text{DALY share}$, then renormalising. Statistical significance of the targeting strategy versus random disease selection was assessed through a permutation test (10,000 iterations selecting 10 random diseases and comparing the resulting combined r_s).

Data Availability

All processed datasets, analysis code, and the complete disease mapping dictionary are available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19534200>. Source data: OpenAlex (<https://openalex.org>, CC0 licence); GBD 2023 (<https://vizhub.healthdata.org/gbd-results/>).